

A Comparison of Stress Levels of MBBS Student in SRVSMC Shivpuri Central India

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Abstract:

The MBBS curriculum is more stressful as it requires students to complete theory lessons in various subjects in a short period. Again, it takes some stress to learn. MBBS students are a bit stressed as they are new to the subject. Through a survey, 300 students were selected for the study. A questionnaire for medical students was used. In this study, female students have highly significantly more stress in Academic Related Stressors, Interpersonal and Intrapersonal Related Stressors, Teaching and Learning Related Stressors, Social Related Stressors, Dive and Desire Related Stressors, and Group Activities Related Stressors.

Keywords: Interpersonal and Intrapersonal, Stressor, Group Activities.

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Introduction

In this study, we discuss the new age MBBS courses in India are very attractive streams. Medical courses in India are very demanding for students and involve emotional aspects as well, sometimes making a career in medical education very stressful [1]. The term stress was first employed in a biological context by endocrinologist Hans Selye in the 1930s. Stress refers to the consequence of the failure of an organism – human or another animal – to respond adequately to mental, emotional, or physical demands whether actual or imagined.

Many people suffer from stress in their daily lives, and there is a strong link between stress and mental health. Stress is an emotional disturbance or change caused by a stressor. Learning requires some stress in medical school [2]. Stress that stimulates and promotes learning is called "beneficial stress", and stress that inhibits or hinders learning is called "unfavorable stress" [2]. The same stressors may be perceived differently by different medical students depending on their cultural background, personal qualities, experiences, and coping skills. Academic-related stressors (ARS) refer to any scholastic, university, college, educational, or student events that cause stress on students. A study reported that top stressors were tests and examinations, time pressure, and getting behind in work as well as

conflicting demands, not getting work done within the time planned, and heavy workload [3]. Another study reported that students who are perfectionists (high self-expectations) are at greater risk for psychological distress [4]. It is perhaps due to high self-expectation to do well in examinations [5]. Interpersonal and intrapersonal-related stressors (IRS) refer to any form of relationships between and within individuals that cause stress. Intrapersonal conflict, interpersonal interaction, and relationships were reported as stressors for medical students, such as poor motivation to learn, and conflict with other students, teachers, and personnel [6]. Teaching and learning-related stressors refer to any events related to teaching or learning that cause stress. A different study reported that dissatisfaction with the quality of education, with lectures, with guidance and feedback from teachers, and with recognition of work done as well as the uncertainty of what is expected from the students was also perceived as a stressor [7]. Social-related stressors refer to any form of community and societal relationships that cause stress.

A study reported that the level of dissatisfaction with social activities was associated with psychological distress among medical students [6]. Impulsive and Needy Stressors are any form of

internal or external force that influences a person's attitudes, feelings, thoughts, and behaviors and results in stress. Various studies have reported that political and family pressures, fear of making the wrong career choice, and reluctance to study medicine have been identified as stressors for medical students[6][3]. All stressors were related to students' motivation to study medicine. A group activity stressor is any group event or interaction that causes stress. This is understandable since most medical education activities involve group work. So, it is easy to fall into trouble if there are difficulties in group activities.

The group learning environment, including the mentor's work, and interactions with peers and patients induced little stress [8]. Stress can affect the body acutely or chronically. Acute stress affects the body in the short term and chronic stress affects the body in the long term [9]. Stress can also increase social and economic losses and reduce a country's competitiveness [10]. Chronic stress is associated with abnormal functioning of the autonomic nervous system [11] [12]. Therefore, stress is undoubtedly one of the main factors contributing to the development of chronic diseases [13] [14].

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at the Department of Community Medicine, Shrimant Rajmata Viharaje Shindia Medical College (SRVSMC), Shivpuri, and central India. The Medical Student Questionnaire (MSSQ) was used in this study. The 50 factors were grouped into six domains, or stressor groups, academic stressors, intrapersonal and interpersonal stressors, teaching and learning stressors, social stressors, stressors related to needs and desires, and stressors related to group activities. is made up. This is a self-report questionnaire and each item represents a specific stressor. Items are rated in fewer than 5 categories. . e.0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 are stress intensities. This study was conducted from January 2023 to August 2023. Students heard about research. Written informed consent was obtained from each student. The questionnaires were distributed to 300 MBBS students during January 2023, and 300 questionnaires were returned. By analyzing this questionnaire, students with chronic diseases were excluded from the study, and a total of 260 subjects were selected, including 190 boys students and 70 girls students.

Graph 1: Distribution of subjects in boys and girls groups

Table 1: Comparison of Boys and Girls Stress

Stressor groups	No of Boys students	No of Girls students	Boys students		Girls students		t-test	P-Value
			Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation		
Academic Related Stressors	190	70	54.49	10.33	64.87	4.77	3.20	p < 0.05
Interpersonal and Intrapersonal Related Stressors	190	70	52.41	3.54	67.79	3.95	9.87	p < 0.05

Teaching and Learning Related Stressors	190	70	61.05	6.81	73.79	5.75	3.95	p < 0.05
Social related stressors	190	70	57.33	3.50	72.90	4.04	3.36	p < 0.05
Drive and desire related stressors	190	70	53.46	7.55	63.38	5.24	4.95	p < 0.05
Group Activities Related Stressors	190	70	51.90	9.75	62.62	7.50	4.05	p < 0.05

Results

Statistical analysis was done by using SPSS 24.0 statistical software. The statistical test used was a t-test, and the stress levels between boys and girls were compared for each stress factor group. The results are shown in Table 1, and female students were found to be more stressed in terms of academic stress ($p < 0.05$), interpersonal stress ($p < 0.05$), and teaching/learning stress ($p < 0.05$), stress factors related to social factors ($p < 0.05$), stress factors related to needs and desires ($p < 0.05$), and stress factors related to group activities ($p < 0.05$), girl students experienced more stress in all groups compared to boys students.

Discussion

Stress is an essential part of the fast pace of life. Medical students experience stress because the curriculum is highly stressful. In this study, it was found that girls students have more stress towards Academic Related Stressors than boys students. This may be due to the excess consciousness of girls students towards examination systems, assessment methods, grading methods, academic schedule, student activities related to academic events such as getting poor marks in examinations, the high self-expectations to do well in studies, a large amount of content to be studied, having difficulty to understand the content, lack of time to revise, etc. girls students have more stress towards Interpersonal and Intrapersonal Related Stressors than boys students. Interpersonal stressors generally relate to relationships between individuals including verbal, physical, and emotional abuse caused by other persons, and conflict with personnel, teachers, colleagues, and staff. Thus girls students may be more conscious regarding this matter than boys students. girls students experience more stress towards Teaching and Learning Related Stressors than boys students and this may be due to the appropriateness of tasks given by teachers to students, teachers' competency to supervise and teach students, quality of feedback given by teachers to students, recognition and support given by teachers to students, and clarity of

learning objectives given by teachers to students. The girls students may react more towards these matters than boys students. Social-related stressors relate to leisure time with family and friends, working with the public, time for self, working interruption by others, and facing patients' problems. Drive and desire-related stressors relate to unwillingness to study medicine due to various reasons such as not being one's choice to study it, wrongly choosing the course, parents wish to study medicine.

The stress associated with group activities is usually related to group discussions, group presentations, and other expectations of success. Regarding all types of activity, there are no significant differences in stress levels, and similar responses are observed in both boys and girls.

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